

BLENDED COACHING SESSIONS AND PRESENCE IN DEVELOPING THE CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

ABEL T. MOZO¹

DELON A. CHING²

abbel.mozo@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0003-1435-4371^{1,2}

Cagbalete Island National High School, Cagbalete, Mauban, Quezon, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

To enhance the quality of learning and improve the skills of the students, these are some of the educators' goals in every instruction. Mathematics as one of the major subjects in high school and perceived by the students as a difficult subject, mathematics educators should create a strategized delivery of teaching and learning in improving the Critical Thinking Skills of the students, particularly in the current situation. This study introduced the Blended Coaching Sessions and Presence which assessed its effect in improving the Critical Thinking Skills. This study utilized the descriptive and correlational design of research participated by 40 of Cagbalete Island National High School grade-nine students of the academic year 2020-2021. The result showed a significant relationship between the blended coaching sessions and the level of critical thinking skills of the students-respondents, which imply that the use of blended coaching sessions affects the performance of students. Also, the result showed that a significant relationship between the coaching presence of teacher and the level of critical thinking skills of the students-respondents, which imply that the coaching presence of teacher affect the performance of the respondents. It was concluded that the blended coaching sessions and coaching presence of teachers is significantly related to the level of critical thinking skills of the students.

Keywords: Blended Session, Coaching, Presence, Critical Skills, Online